

SOCIAL SCIENCES

PROGRAM FOR THE EMPIRICAL RESEARCH OF PLASTIC SURGERY AS A RESOURCE FOR IDENTITY CONSTRUCTION

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Abstract

The article reveals an in-depth interview method for studying the relationship between body modifications through plastic surgery and the processes of constructing female identity in modern society. Based on the presented method, it is concluded that the body and identity are interconnected, appearance is significant for the individual in terms of his social identity and perception by other people in the process of interaction.

Keywords: body, identity, plastic surgery, interview, society.

The body today acts as an important factor for inclusion in social interaction and the formation of social identity. So, according to E. Goffman, it is extremely important for an individual that it is his appearance that constantly informs everyone with whom he intersects about his social identity.

According to Giddens, the body in the late modern era is an integral part of the reflective project of the self - the invention of the self. The body is not only a physical object that a person «possesses», it is also presented as a system of behavior, a source of practices and an active involvement of an individual in everyday interactions that an individual needs to maintain a sense of his own identity. The body and the identity of the individual mutually influence each other in accordance with one or another lifestyle, the cultivation of one or another bodily regime as a conscious choice [1].

Currently, there is an increase in the popularity of plastic surgery, both in the world and in our country, which can illustrate the increasing importance of the body for the individual and his identity.

Moreover, body care practices have become one of the markers of the era of consumerism. As J. Baudrillard wrote, «today it is necessary to serve the body. If you do not serve the body, if you sin by not paying attention to it, you will be punished» [2].

The problematic situation that sets the context for the study is related to the contradiction between the growing popularity of body modifications, which has a positive effect on the plastic surgery market, and the lack of knowledge of the motivations for plastic surgery and their consequences for the social life of individuals.

Object of study: patients of the plastic surgery clinic.

Subject of research: interaction of body modifications with the help of plastic surgery and the identity of patients.

The purpose of the empirical study: using the method of in-depth interviews, to study the relationship between body modifications through plastic surgery and the processes of constructing female identity in modern society.

Tasks of empirical research:

- Identify the motives for the implementation of plastic surgery.

- To study the influence of society on the formation of ideas about the normative female physicality.
- To study the role of plastic surgery in the construction of female identity.

Research questions:

- What motives influence an individual's decision about plastic surgery?

- How does the social environment influence the idea of female physicality?

- What role does plastic surgery play in constructing an individual's identity?

The study was conducted on the basis of the Department of Aesthetic Surgery at the Diagnostic and Treatment Center «AvisMed» in the city of Novosibirsk. According to the description of the center on its official website, «AvisMed is the largest multidisciplinary medical center in Novosibirsk. The aesthetic medicine clinic at the AvisMed LDC «is an association of medical cosmetology and plastic surgery, today it is one of the priority areas of the LDC» [3].

To implement the empirical study, the method of in-depth interviews with patients of the plastic surgery clinic was chosen.

The interview was conducted on the basis of the guide, which includes several blocks of questions:

1. Biographical block.

2. The influence of social relations on the perception and construction of corporality.

3. The influence of social relations on the perception and construction of corporality.

The purpose of the questions in the biographical block was to find out how long ago the patients thought about plastic surgery, what influenced the patients' decisions about bodily modification through plastic surgery, and what event was the final «push» for plastic surgery.

The second block is devoted to the influence of social relations on the perception and construction of physicality. The questions in this block were aimed at studying the influence of the external environment on the patients' perception of the standards of corporality and how the social environment affects the decision to undergo bodily modification.

The task of the third block of in-depth interviews was to find out how the bodily modification affected

the patient's internal sense of his status, as well as relationships with other people.

Each interview was transcribed. Open coding was chosen as the data processing method.

The target sample of informants was formed by the method of available cases.

The meaning of this method lies in the fact that the formation of the sample is carried out in the most accessible way from the standpoint of the researcher [4]. It should be noted that the search for informants with experience in plastic surgery and willing to conduct an in-depth interview about the causes of plastic surgery and the impact of plastic surgery on the patient's life was quite difficult - not every patient of the plastic surgery clinic agreed to a frank conversation about bodily modifications.

An important criterion for the selection of respondents was that the operation must have been performed at least one month ago. The respondent must have experience of being in a society with a new look, since the study was supposed to assess how external experience influenced the social life of patients and their inner sense of self.

10 girls from 20 to 39 years old took part in the interview:

- 8 of which underwent plastic surgery only for rhinoplasty (plastic surgery to restore the nose or correct it);

- 1 patient who underwent mammoplasty (a surgical operation aimed at changing the shape and size of the mammary glands) and liposuction of the abdominal cavity;

- 1 patient who underwent mammoplasty and rhinoplasty.

Operationalization of basic concepts:

The normative body is understood as the parameters and practices of the physical body that correspond to the value-normative standards of a particular society and certain social groups.

Stigma is «a quality that betrays some shameful property of an individual, and the nature of this quality is determined not by the quality itself, but by the attitude towards it» [5]. With a sufficient mismatch between the normative expectations of society (virtual identity) and the actual identity (that is, the one that the individual actually possesses), stigmatization of the individual occurs.

The stigmatized individual feels that «no matter what others say to him, in fact they do not accept him and are not ready to interact with him on an equal footing» [5]. The result of stigmatization in this case is a damaged identity. Stigmatized people do not have full social acceptance and are constantly striving to change their social identity.

According to Anthony Giddens, the essence of personal identity is that it presupposes a reflective consciousness. Identity is what a person realizes through the expression «self-consciousness». It is necessary to give a clearer understanding of identity:

Self-identity is a reflective project for which the individual is responsible. The individual becomes what he makes of himself.

The concept of «the body-we-make» is particularly suited to those social theories that point to risk and uncertainty as essential conditions. According to E. Giddens, the most important existential dimension of the life of a modern person is total doubt, and the surrounding global world is subjectively felt as existing far beyond the limits of individual control capabilities. In this situation, managing the characteristics of one's body becomes the most accessible way to create and maintain the continuity of a self-identical «I», or self-identity – «a constant feeling of a continuous spiritual and bodily personality» [6].

Social construction of a sense of identity is the process of using commodities such as clothing, shoes, popular music, or playing a certain sport to identify oneself as a member of a particular group or, conversely, to emphasize one's being outside of it.

The modern sociology of corporality considers the body as a space for the embodiment of personal identity and a means of self-expression. In many studies of female corporality, attention is paid to the significance of the corporal incarnation for the identity of the individual. Thus, the body and identity are interconnected, appearance is significant for the individual in terms of his social identity and perception by other people in the process of interaction.

Based on the analysis of the interviews, it can be said that the transformation of physicality had a generally positive effect on the life and self-perception of all patients. So, according to their own statements, the consequences of plastic surgery were reflected both in the internal feeling of comfort and self-confidence, and in the relationship with other people. However, in the course of the study, it was important to study exactly how plastic surgery affected the identity of the respondents. Thanks to the study, it was revealed that the reactions of the near environment are not of great importance in making decisions about the construction of the individual's corporality. Thus, negative reactions were ignored by our respondents - the girls did not succumb to excuses and disapproving attitude towards bodily modifications on the part of close people. The support and motivation for plastic surgery from friends was noted by informants as a consequence of the decision to have plastic surgery, and not the reason.

As for the influences of mass culture, the girls acknowledged the influence of mass culture on the formation of normative physicality, which, however, speaking about their own transformation of appearance, the girls reject the influence of modern canons of beauty, focusing on the state of personal comfort and harmony. At the same time, the majority of respondents who underwent plastic surgery criticized both those who try to excessively follow the standard female corporality, and those who go beyond the normative bodies (in most cases this concerned obese corporality). Thus, we can conclude that for the interviewed girls, the balance in appearance is important, the «golden mean», which is at the intersection of internal comfort and the prevailing standards of female beauty in society.

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